

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AND ITS IMPACT OUR ECONOMY.

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Annotation: This article highlights the importance attached to foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the innovative technologies needed to study them.

Keywords: Foreign language, game, innovative technology, technological tools, methods, techniques.

Introduction: After the independence of our country, interest in teaching foreign languages has increased and many opportunities have been created for young people. As the first President Islam Karimov said, "At present, great importance is attached to the teaching of foreign languages in our country. this is also not in vain. Today, there is no need to underestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take their rightful place in the world community, and for our people, who are building their great future in cooperation with our foreign partners. " As a logical continuation of these considerations, the Presidential Decree of 10 December 2012 "On Measures to Further Improve the System of Teaching Foreign Languages" expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages. New methods and requirements for foreign language teaching in our country have been developed in accordance with the Recommendations of the European Framework for Assessment of Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers (CEFR). textbooks have been created for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms are equipped with stands and new information and communication technologies. The demand for learning a foreign language is growing day by day. foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading,

reading, listening comprehension and speaking), each of which is given specific concepts and skills.

The main part: Educational technology is the effective use of modern information technology in the educational process. It also aims to improve the quality and effectiveness of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies in the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages to using such information and communication technologies in foreign language learning. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of foreign language learning (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer, player, CDs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. This requires the student to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is the ability of students to know and use information and communication technologies.

Education is determined by the purpose, content, personality of the teacher, the nature of the students' initial knowledge, how well they know and are able to reinforce the words learned in English, and many other factors. In a pamphlet entitled as noted, when science is mastered through teaching, the virtues are acquired through education, and thus its impact on the economy as well. Teaching is the basis not only for the training of the mind, but also for general spiritual perfection, including moral perfection. Teaching and upbringing are interrelated and are different ways of spiritual development of the individual. The unit is subject to certain laws and is generally philosophical according to the methodology. Nowadays, there are enough opportunities and conditions for the development of English speech. A variety of creative and moving games, activities, exercises, trips and observations - all add to the meaning of children's lives. The importance of role-playing games in the development of children's speech should be emphasized. These games allow for a wide range of communication and exchange of ideas. A meaningful

life brings children closer together, teaches them to live in a harmonious community, prevents quarrels and resentment. without their speech developing empty, they are about something they can't speak, they find it difficult to ask for anything, their vocabulary grows very slowly; boredom creates conflict, which in turn negatively affects the proper development of a child's speech.

One of the most effective ways is to teach and learn a foreign language using modern technology. In this process, including: - when using computers, the student can watch and listen to videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language; - It is possible to listen and watch radio broadcasts in foreign languages and TV programs; - use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are more traditional methods; - CD players are available. The use of these tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students [1]. Today, interactive games are becoming a tradition in schools. It is well known that a variety of play-based activities help students demonstrate their abilities, focus, increase their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basis of the use of game technology is an activity that activates and accelerates the student.

In addition to visual aids, work on the dictionary is carried out through exhibitions in the classroom, as well as through acquaintance with the environment. In the process of acquainting students with the surrounding objects, events, plants, animals and so on, we say their names, qualities, characteristics in English words. the selector introduces students into their speech using selective and dialogic speech, which helps them engage in oral communication with their peers in English. Not only do they teach students to understand the translation of words, but they also become accustomed to actively using these words in speech. A dictionary is a building block of language. Grammar, on the other hand, determines how words change in a sentence and how they are connected. In addition, grammar determines the construction model of the language (word-maker, word-changer). The earlier a student learns all the grammatical forms of English, the faster he will develop both mentally and verbally. If the grammatical aspect of speech in a student is formed incorrectly, mental development is delayed. The teacher must correct grammatical

errors in children's speech in each type of activity and game. A grammatical error that is not corrected in a timely manner will reinforce the child's speech and lead to grammatical errors in the speech of other children who are listening to it. However, in specially organized games, it is necessary to work on warning of the child's speech or these negative aspects, and to eliminate grammatical errors in the child's speech in a timely manner.

Psychologists say that the psychological mechanisms of playful activity are based on the fundamental needs of the individual to express himself, to find a stable place in life, to self-manage, to realize his potential. At the heart of any game should be generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Learning games should be based on the subjects. During the games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a normal lesson and is more comfortable. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a way of teaching. Students are interested in playful lessons, they strive to win, and the teacher uses them to educate the student. The student is interested in believing that he or she can play, speak, listen, understand, and write in English [2]. We know that in the current educational process, the student has to be a subject. Focusing on more interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach students to think independently. Today, English teachers use the following innovative methods, based on the experience of United States states and English educators: - "Creative Problem Solving" is the beginning of the story. students are referred to the student judgment; - "Merry Riddles" Teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn words they are unfamiliar with and find the answer to a riddle; - Quick answers help to increase the effectiveness of the lesson; - "Warm-up exercises" to use a variety of games in the classroom to engage students in the lesson [3]; - Pantomime can be used in a class where very difficult topics need to be explained, or when students are tired of writing exercises; - A chain story method helps to develop students' oral skills; - Acting characters This method can be used in all types of lessons. Professionals such as Interpreter, Translator, Writer, and Poet can participate in the class and talk to students; - Poets

and writers such as U.Shakespeare, A.Navoi, R.Burns can be "invited". At the same time, using the words of wisdom they say in class will help young people grow up to be perfect people; - The "When pictures speak" method is more convenient and helps to teach English, to develop students' oral speech, it is necessary to use thematic pictures; - Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to attend classes at the same time, which saves time [4].

Conclusion: As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own set of advantages. All of these methods involve collaboration between teacher and student, active participation of the student in the educational process [5]. In short, the use of innovative methods in English lessons develops students' logical thinking skills, fluency, and the ability to respond quickly and accurately. Such methods stimulate the student's desire for knowledge. The student tries to prepare well for the lessons. This makes students active participants in the learning process. As the education system sets itself the task of nurturing a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future we will contribute to the further development of effective use of innovative technologies by future teachers. possible.

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